

Sanctuary of Artemis at Brauron

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Entry tags: Brauron, Archaeological Site, Greece, Attica, Religious Group, Ancient Mediterranean, Greek Polis Religions, Aegean, Greek Cult, Greek Religions, Religious Place

Brauron was an important religious site for the Athenians, particularly for women and young girls, between the 6th and 3rd centuries BCE. Prior to its usage as a sanctuary, Brauron was a flourishing settlement between 2000 and 1300 BCE. Subsequent to the abandonment of the site as a place of habitation, Brauron attained a high level of religious importance during the 6th century under the reign of the Peisistratids. Religious worship at Brauron predominantly focused on the Brauronian Artemis for her attributes as a goddess of childbirth and for guidance for the transition from childhood to marriage. Young girls, beginning around the age of seven, would participate in coming-of-age rituals at the site and call upon Artemis Brauronia during their first menstruation, marriage, and pregnancy. The two major festivals associated with this sanctuary, namely, the Brauronia and the Arkteia, are mainly attested by Aristophanes' plays *Lysistrata* and *Peace*. Iphigenia also appears to have been an important figure of worship at Brauron, due to her connection as a sacrifice to the goddess in the events leading to the Trojan War. The extant Doric temple dates to approximately 500 BCE with a pillared porch with three interior rooms. North of the temple is a Doric stoa notable for its irregular Π shape and numerous dining (or sleeping) rooms. The irregular shape of the stoa coincides with the layout of the Brauroneion on the Athenian Acropolis, which replaced Brauron as the cult site for Artemis Brauronia after the sanctuary's abandonment in the late 4th century BCE. To the west of the stoa is a stone bridge dating to the 5th century BCE, the only one of its kind found on mainland Greece according to Papadimitriou. Found in situ alongside the temple and stoa walls were rows of stela bases that held inscriptions listing dedications and offerings given to the goddess dating from the mid-4th century BCE and later, copies of which were found in the Brauroneion on the Acropolis. Southeast of the temple is the so-called Heroon of Iphigenia. This heroon is a small, rock-cut shrine with evidence of the existence of rooms inside the cave. Located near the temple is a 16th century (CE) church dedicated to St. George. Following the Persians' sacking of the site in 480 BCE and the flooding of the local Erasinos River, it appears the site never fully recovered, and the cult shifted to the Athenian Acropolis. An inscription dating to the 3rd century BCE attests to building inspections taking place following the flooding of the Erasinos River, however, the lack of repairs is further indication of the site's abandonment.

Date Range: 2000 BCE - 200 BCE

Region: Brauron

Region tags: Europe, Southern Europe, Greece, Eastern Mediterranean, Attica

Archaeological site of Brauron, around 30 kilometers east of Athens on the Aegean coast.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Cleland, L. 2005. The symbiosis of description: some reflections on fabric and colour in the Brauron inventories. In Cleland et al. *The Clothed Body in the Ancient World*. London: Oxbow Books: 87 - 95.
- Source 2: Bouras Charalampos. 1967. *Hē Anastēlōsis Tēs Stoas Tēs Braurōnos : Ta Architektonika Tes Problēmata*. Athēnai: Hyperesia Archaioyton kai Anasteloseos.
- Source 3: Themelis Petros G. 1971. *Brauron: Guide to the Site and Museum*. Athens: Apollo Editions.
- Source 1: Papadopoulou, Chryssanthi. 2018. "Attic Sanctuaries." *Archaeological Reports* 64 (64): 103-12. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0570608418000224>.
- Source 2: Hollinshead, Mary Brooks Berg. 1979. "Legend, Cult, and Architecture at Three Sanctuaries of Artemis." ProQuest Dissertations Publishing.
- Source 3: Rietveld, Kyra. 2022. "Iconography of the Cult of Artemis in the Greek Classical and Imperial Periods". ProQuest Dissertations Publishing.
- Source 1: Papadimitriou, J. (1963) "The Sanctuary of Artemis at Brauron" in *Scientific American*, Vol. 206, No. 6, pp. 111-120.
- Source 2: Linders, Tullia. 1972. *Studies in the Treasure Records of Artemis Brauronia Found in Athens*. Lund: [P. Aestrom].
- Source 3: Ekroth, G. (2003) "Inventing Iphigeneia? On Euripides and the Cultic Construction of Brauron" in *Kernos*, No. 16, pp. 59-118.
- Source 1: Kahil, L. (1983). *The Mythological Repertoire of Brauron*. *Ancient Greek Art and Iconography*, 231-244.
- Source 2: Mikalson, J. D. (2010). *Ancient Greek religion* (2nd ed.). West Sussex: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Source 3: Blundell, Sue., and Margaret Williamson. 1998. *The Sacred and the Feminine in Ancient Greece*. London :: Routledge.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: http://odysseus.culture.gr/h/3/eh355.jsp?obj_id=2419
- Source 1 Description: The Hellenic Ministry of Culture's description of the site
- Source 2 URL: <https://inscriptions.packhum.org/book/5?location=1701>
- Source 2 Description: Includes inscriptions from many different publications and has many of the inscriptions pertaining to the Brauron inventories, particularly IG II2 1514-30.
- Source 3 URL: http://odysseus.culture.gr/h/4/eh42.jsp?obj_id=3570
- Source 3 Description: The Hellenic Ministry of Culture's description of the Archaeological Museum of Brauron

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1948-1963

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: The Sanctuary of Artemis at Brauron. The site was excavated under the supervision of Ioannis Papadimitriou and the auspices of the Archaeological Society at Athens. However much of the information and reports from the excavations remain unpublished.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

– Water source

– Cave

– Other [specify]: The archaeological site of Brauron is located in a wetland environment.

Notes: The sanctuary itself was established on the banks of the Erasinos River. To the northwest of the temple there was a sacred spring with a small stream that ran along the west side of the site. Thousands of dedications were found in the bed of the stream, with the majority pre-dating 480 BCE. It is possible that the dedications were hidden in the river as a way to hide them from the invading Persians prior to the sacking of the site. To the southeast of the stoa is the cave sanctuary, or heroon, of Iphigenia.

Type of elevation

– Hill

Notes: The southern part of the sanctuary is built on top of a small hill on which the heroon of Iphigenia and the Church of St. George are located.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Terracing

– Trackway or road-surface

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: The sanctuary at Brauron was largely abandoned as a human settlement around 1600 BCE and predominantly served as a place of religious worship. The surrounding area was largely rural.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Brauron was an important place of pilgrimage and as a result there was a roadway connecting Athens to Brauron.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: Brauron was close to a number of settlements in antiquity (most notably, Athens), however, to call any place of habitation in the ancient Greek world would be entirely anachronistic. The religion of the ancient Greeks was embedded within all aspects of daily life meaning that there was no such thing as a non-religious settlement.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

Notes: The extant temple of Artemis on the site dates to c. 500 BCE, however, there is archaeological evidence that this temple was built on top of older foundations dating to around the 8th century BCE. The Doric temple was designed in the traditional Doric

manner with a pillared porch, prodomos, cella, and adyton and was constructed on an east-west orientation. Two rows of columns inside the temple divided the interior space into three naves and the temple itself was approximately 66 feet long and 33.5 feet wide.

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: Evidence for human occupation at the site dates to at least the Neolithic period into the Mycenaean period, flourishing from 3500-1300 BCE. The earliest temple to Artemis has foundations dating to at least the 8th century BCE with the extant Doric temple being dated to c. 500 BCE. North of the temple is the Doric Π-shaped stoa dating to the late 5th century BCE. A number of rooms have been discovered on the north and west sides of the stoa which Papadimitriou posits were the residence rooms for the 'arktoi' or priestesses of Artemis. Found alongside the stoa walls were a number of stelae bases which once held the inventories of the treasury from the sanctuary. Copies of these inscriptions were found in the Brauroneion on the Athenian Acropolis and provide lists of offerings dedicated to the goddess. West of the stoa is a stone bridge, also dating to the late 5th century BCE, crossing over the stream which flowed from the sacred spring (northwest of the temple). The bridge was 30 feet long and 30 feet wide, with horizontal stone slabs supported by a series of walls parallel to the stream. Papadimitriou cites this as the only bridge of its kind from the 5th century found on mainland Greece. Uphill and southeast from the temple is the mid 5th century rock-cut heroon of Iphigenia. This shrine is 24.5 feet long and 14.5 feet wide. A small number of rooms were found, built out of stone and mortar, buried under fallen boulders. Papadimitriou suggests that the position of these boulders implies that the shrine and rooms were once situated within a cave. South of the temple is the 16th century CE Church of St. George which Papadimitriou suggests is situated on the site of an altar associated with earlier cult worship.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The site had several construction phases with the 6th century temple being the oldest structure in the sanctuary, followed by the 5th century heroon of Iphigenia and western retaining wall, and the late 5th century Doric stoa and stone bridge.

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

- ↳ Worship:
 - Communal

– Sacrificial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Notes: The Doric stoa, according to Bouras, was never fully completed.

- ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - Yes

- ↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

- Other [specify]: Flood. The Erasinos River flooded some time between 400 and 300 BCE evidenced through portions of the architecture being uncovered embedded in mud.

- Other [specify]: Brauron was damaged by the Persians in 480 BCE with Pausanias reporting that the cult statue was brought to Susa following the invasion.

- ↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

- As the result of war

- Notes: Brauron was one of the sites affected by the Persian sack of Attica during the events of the Persian Wars in 480 BCE.

- ↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

- Natural phenomena

- Notes: Flooding of the nearby Erasinos River caused damage to the structures. A 4th/3rd century inscription, SEG 52.104, found at the site indicates that a number of buildings on the site were in need of repair.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

Notes: Partially reconstructed

↳ In antiquity

– Once

Notes: The temple of Artemis was rebuilt in the 6th century over older foundations dating to, at the earliest, the 8th century BCE.

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Artemis Brauronia was the dominant deity being worshipped at Brauron, attested by inscriptions, dedicatory offerings, and ancient authors.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Notes: There appears to have been some form of heroic worship of Iphigenia at Brauron. This is attested by the heroon, identification in inscriptions, and her association with Artemis as both a priestess and sacrificial victim in myth.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: The tyrant Peisistratus is credited with bringing the cult of Artemis Brauronia to Athens and for increasing the importance of the religious worship of the cult.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Notes: The heroon of Iphigenia, according to Euripides' 'Iphigenia in Tauris', was believed to be her place of burial. However, no archaeological evidence has yet been uncovered which supports this theory.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Notes: Greek religion in general functioned in a reciprocal framework wherein humans gave offerings and prayers to the gods in order to gain something from them in return, this place of worship functioned according to this model.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: There is a retaining wall to the west which protects much of the buildings within the sanctuary and the heroon is located on the top of a terraced hill.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The temple was likely the most important in terms of religious significance, apart from the altar which has yet to be uncovered, as it housed the cult image of the goddess as well as offerings dedicated to her. In terms of magnitude, the stoa would have been used more frequently by priestesses for dining or sleeping and potentially for religious rituals.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 50

Notes: Based on a visual analysis of the site, it is probable that around 50% of the site is taken up by built monuments. However, no official analysis has been undertaken to ascertain the veracity of this number.

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 1263.6

Notes: The Doric stoa is the largest building on the site, though it is irregular in shape and this area estimate was done with the longest sides (north and east) of the structure. The actual dimensions are: North wing stylobate: 29.19 m x ca. 6.2 m; west wing stylobate: 25.42 m long; east wing stylobate: 43.29 m long; Parastas: ca. 39.8 m x ca. 6 m.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 3.65

Notes: This is the height of the columns which survive from the Doric stoa, since the roof and other supporting walls have not survived this is the best estimate for the overall height of the structure.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 395.75

Notes: Heroon of Iphigenia: 7.75 x 4.45 m Stone Bridge: 9 x 9 m Doric Temple: 19.2 x 10.35 m Doric Stoa: north wing stylobate: 29.19 m x ca. 6.2 m; west wing stylobate: 25.42 m long; east wing stylobate: 43.29 m long; Parastas: ca. 39.8 m x ca. 6 m.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

Notes: There is evidence that mortar was used for the small rooms found in context with the heroon.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Wood
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

Notes: A poros quarry from Artemida, part of the large Porias poros quarry, was the primary source of building material for the sanctuary. It is characterized by a yellow colour and being a relatively soft stone. The use of limestone in structures present on the site is also attested.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials
– Field doesn't know

Decoration

Is decoration present:
– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Field doesn't know

Notes: Due to the poorly preserved nature of the site and lack of detailed publication it is difficult to determine what, if any, fragmentary architectural elements belonged to which building.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries
– Yes

Notes: Traces of triglyphs were uncovered in context with the temple, implying the use of triglyphs as part of the architectural decoration.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: A nearly life-sized goat head was uncovered near the temple which Themelis has argued may imply the existence of pedimental sculpture on the temple. Bear imagery also played an important role within the cult and religious worship of Artemis Brauronia.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: If triglyphs count as geometric or abstract then yes there is geometric decoration present.

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

Notes: It is possible that there was interior decoration which would have been hidden from view, however, this is difficult to discern based off of current reports and the extant remains.

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– No

Notes: There is no surviving cult statue from the site. Pausanias reports that the old wooden one was removed to Susa by the Persians in 480 BCE.

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Of the thousands of dedicatory offerings which have been found at the site, many of them include Artemis as the main subject matter. A series of statuettes were uncovered depicting Artemis Kourotrophos, a triple bodied Hekate, and a fragmentary statuette of Cybele have been found. The torso of an Artemis-like figure has also been uncovered but not confidently identified as the goddess.

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: There are a multitude of statues and statuettes depicting young children, both male and female, that have been uncovered at Brauron. These depictions date predominantly to the 4th or 3rd centuries BCE and include children as young as infants to prepubescent youths.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone,

clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: The 'Relief of the Gods', dating to around 400 BCE, depicted at least four deities: Zeus, Leto, Apollo, and Artemis. Kahil theorizes that Iphigenia would have also been present in this scene, due to fragmentary remains attributed to this relief. She believes that Iphigenia was included in this scene either as a torchbearer, perhaps implicating a religious ritual, or holding the reins of a chariot and thus replacing the figure of Artemis in the main scene. If the second argument is true, then the fragmented figure found in context with the relief may be interpreted as a statue of Artemis being carried on the chariot. A fragmentary relief, potentially part of an altar, depicts Dionysus, Leto, and other figures. There are also numerous reliefs depicting the goddess alongside various animals, such as stags and goats, and her mortal worshippers.

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Numerous reliefs have been found depicting scenes which one would have experienced as a worshipper at Brauron or in daily life. There is a late 5th century relief depicting a seated woman with an epinetron on her knee, and thus engaged in weaving. Three 4th century reliefs depict Artemis receiving worshippers of men, women, and children.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

Notes: There were a number of inscriptions placed outside the stoa, however, there is no indication that these inscriptions served any type of decorative function. Rather they served as inventories for the dedications and offerings given to the goddess by her worshippers.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: The only indications that this sanctuary is associated with tombs/burials are from Euripides' and Papadimitriou's interpretation that the cave shrine is the final resting place of Iphigenia mentioned by Euripides. There are also Mycenaean chamber tombs present at the site, however, they are not associated with the later cult worship.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

Notes: The grave goods found at the site are exclusively related to the Mycenaean era of

occupation and not with the later sanctuary. Of the grave goods uncovered are gold jewelry, bronze swords, and dozens of lead weights from a fishing net.

↳ Significant value:
Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value
– Yes

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:
– Yes

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Other
–Yes [specify]: N/A

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:
– No

↳ In cemetery:
– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:
– No

↳ Domestic context:
Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity
– No

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: N/A

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Yes

Notes: A chthonic fertility deity, perhaps Iphigenia, was present at the cult site and became merged with Artemis Brauronia. While Artemis was not inherently a chthonic deity, this characteristic of the goddess had chthonic ties.

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– No

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: N/A

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Notes: Not unless we consider Iphigenia in this regard.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

Notes: There was a wooden cult statue of Artemis located in the temple.

Is the cult statue hidden:

– Yes

Notes: Partially, the statue would not have been entirely visible at all times due to the architectural orientation of Greek temples.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: This communication is done through offerings, prayers, sacrifice, rituals, etc.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, there is the heroon of Iphigenia which was excavated alongside numerous offerings including mirrors, jewelry, statuettes, and vases.

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: Goats were sacrificed every four years at the Brauronia festival

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– Yes [specify]: There is human sacrifice associated with Artemis Brauronia through connections to other Artemis cults and Iphigenia

Notes: Iphigenia is associated with human sacrifice as she was intended to be offered as a way of appeasing the goddess so the Greeks could set sail for Troy. The cult of Artemis Brauronia is also associated with Artemis Orthia at Sparta, which itself is believed to have involved human sacrifices. The cult of Artemis Tauropolos is also believed to have practiced human sacrifice at some point in time. However, there is no concrete evidence (literary or archaeologically) to support the use of human sacrifice at Brauron.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: There are numerous valuable offerings that have been found at Brauron including jewelry, decorated vases, figurines, and mirrors.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: There were various types of pottery uncovered as well as epinetron (associated with weaving), clothing, and other various garments.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

Notes: Offerings would have been stored in both the temple and stoa, some of which were likely moved to the Brauroneion on the Acropolis at Athens after the Persian invasion. Thousands of offerings largely predating 480 BCE were uncovered in the small stream, though there is no indicated motivation for this apart from attempting to hide these items from the pending invasion.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: While there is no concrete evidence to suggest necessary cleaning, it seems evident that some type of regular maintenance would have been required.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: We know that the temple was rebuilt in the 6th century and a later (3rd century BCE) inscription mentions various buildings on site which were in need of repair, however there is no indication that these repairs were carried out. It does however indicate that some degree of maintenance occurred over time.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:
– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:
– Yes

↳ Birth
– Yes

Notes: Artemis Brauronia was associated with pregnancy and childbirth.

↳ Transition to adulthood
– Yes

Notes: Children, especially girls, would make offerings to Artemis Brauronia in their transitory time between childhood and marriage.

↳ Death
– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Young girls would make offerings to Artemis Brauronia at the time of their first menstruation.

- ↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
 - Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

- ↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:
 - Yes [specify]: Several rooms found in the Doric stoa have been identified as potential dining rooms. However, Papadimitriou has theorized that some of these rooms may have been the residence for the young priestesses of Artemis.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

- ↳ Frequency of festivals
 - specify: The Brauronia Festival occurred every 4 years. The Arkteia was either a smaller ritual established as part of the Brauroneion or a separate festival celebrated with unknown frequency.

- ↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):
 - All members
 - Notes: All members of society were permitted, however, women and young children (especially girls) were the primary attendants at the festivals.

- ↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:
 - No

- ↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
 - number: Unknown

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Elites

– Non-elites

– Religious professionals

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Notes: Not unless praying for protection and health during pregnancy and menstruation counts as healing.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Unknown

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Daily

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: There is evidence for wine used as an intoxicant during festivals and rituals.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Artemis Brauronia was served by priestesses.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: Greek. The priestesses were also likely girls from wealthy families around Attica as evidenced by the daughter of Peisistratus serving as a kanephoros to the goddess.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is some evidence to suggest that the majority of girls taking part in processions and rituals at Brauron were from wealthy citizen families. However, there is little to no evidence

to suggest that all religious specialists at the sanctuary were from elite or non-elite classes.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: If Papadimitriou's interpretation of the stoa rooms is correct then yes, this is where the young priestesses resided.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Lists of the dedication inventories were present at Brauron, and were moved (and copied) to the Brauroneion on the Athenian Acropolis in the 5th/4th century BCE.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No